

Local Anaesthetics. Part—III¹ : Synthesis of 2-(*N*-Substituted or *N,N*-Disubstituted Aminoacetamido)-4-aryl Thiazoles

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Some new 2-(*N*-substituted or *N,N*-disubstituted aminoacetamido)-4-*p*-nitrophenyl, 4-*m*-nitrophenyl, and 4-(2',5'-dimethoxy)phenyl thiazoles have been synthesised. Their hydrochlorides have been screened for local anaesthetic activity by Frog's sciatic plexus method and the activity compared with that of procaine hydrochloride. Among them 2-(*N*-substituted aminoacetamido)-4-*m*-nitrophenylthiazole hydrochlorides are the most potent, almost twice in terms of onset of anaesthesia in comparison with procaine-HCl.

VARIOUS analogues of the well-known local anaesthetic procaine (diethylaminoethyl *p*-aminobenzoate) are still used in clinical practice. Of these Ambucaine² (1a) and Paraethoxycaine³ (1b) are of special interest not only because these compounds exhibit low order of positional specificity for activity but functional groups may even be interchanged at will (e.g. ethoxy for amino).

Lidocaine (2-diethylamino-2',6'-acetoxylicide) is considered one of the most satisfactory local anaesthetics because it is more stable in solution and quick in onset. It was reported⁴ that 4-aryloxy- and 4-alkoxy-2,6-dimethylanilides have greater local anaesthetic activity than procaine.

2-(*t*-Butylamino)-2',6'-propionoxylidide (2) has significantly long lasting local anaesthetic activity and low acute toxicity⁵. 2-Aminopyrrole analogues (3) of lidocaine were prepared⁶ and showed significant local anaesthetic activity by the guinea pig wheal test and also showed antiarrhythmic activity against chloroform-induced ventricular arrhythmias in mice.

(1a) Y = O (CH₃), CH₃, Z = NH₂

(1b) Y = H, Z = OC₂H₅

(2)

(3)

(4)

where X = *p*-nitro, *m*-nitro and 2',5'-dimethoxy.

Keeping these facts in view and that 2-aminothiazole derivatives^{1,7} exhibit marked local anaesthetic activity, the authors have synthesised a series of nitro and dimethoxy-substituted 4-phenyl-2-(*N*-substituted or *N,N*-disubstituted aminoacetamido) thiazoles having the general structure (4).

The starting materials, 2-amino-4-arylthiazoles, were prepared by the condensation of *p*-nitroacetophenone or *m*-nitroacetophenone or 2,5-dimethoxyacetophenone with thiourea in the presence of iodine. The 2-amino-4-arylthiazoles were treated with chloroacetyl chloride in dry benzene to give the corresponding 2-chloroacetamido-4-arylthiazoles. Reaction of these compounds with different primary and secondary amines in presence of potassium carbonate in absolute ethanol yielded 2-(*N*-substituted or *N,N*-disubstituted aminoacetamido)-4-arylthiazoles (Table 1). They were converted into their hydrochlorides by usual methods (Table 2), and evaluated for conduction anaesthesia on frogs by the sciatic plexus method⁸.

Experimental

Melting points were observed with a Gallenkamp apparatus and are uncorrected. Elemental analyses (C, H and N) were carried out on a Coleman Analyser. The ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 720 grating spectrophotometer as nujol mulls, while nmr on a Varian-A60D spectrometer at the probe temperature (44.5°) as CCl₄ or CDCl₃ solutions using tetramethylsilane as an internal standard.

The purity of the compounds was checked by tlc using silica gel G (E. Merck).

2-Amino-4-(2',5'-dimethoxy)phenylthiazole : 2,5-Dimethoxyacetophenone and thiourea were reacted in the presence of iodine¹. The product was crystallized from EtOH as deep brown needles, m.p. 121° (Found : N, 11.90. $C_{11}H_{12}N_2O_3S$ requires N, 11.87%); ν_{max} 3450m, 3330m, 1620m, 1520s, 1500s cm^{-1} ; δ ($CDCl_3$) 3.85 and 3.90 (s, 3H each, for two OCH_3), 5.30 (br, 2H, NH_2), 6.85-7.75 (m, 4H, Ar).

2-Amino-4-m-nitrophenylthiazole : It was obtained from *m*-nitroacetophenone as above, m.p. 185° (requires⁹ 188-90°); ν_{max} (KBr) 3470m, 3320w, 3150m, 1640s, 1550s, 1520s, 1360s, 730m cm^{-1} .

2-Amino-4-p-nitrophenylthiazole : It was prepared as above in 90% yield from *p*-nitroacetophenone, m.p. 282° (crystallised from DMF) (requires⁹ 285-6°); ν_{max} 3440w, 3350w, 3200w, 1640s, 1600s, 1530m, 1500s cm^{-1} .

2-Chloroacetamido-4-(2',5'-dimethoxy)phenylthiazole : To a solution of 2-amino-4-(2',5'-dimethoxy)phenylthiazole (9.7 g) in dry benzene (40 ml) was added dropwise a cooled solution of chloroacetyl chloride (4.0 ml) in dry benzene (15 ml). The reaction mixture was refluxed on a water bath at 80° for 3 h. Benzene and excess chloroacetyl chloride were removed by distillation. The residue was washed with aqueous sodium bicarbonate followed by cold water. The crude product was dried and crystallised from ethanol (65%), m.p. 142° (Found : N, 9.10; S, 10.15. $C_{15}H_{18}ClN_2O_3S$ requires N, 8.95; S, 10.24%). ν_{max} 3250m, 1665s, 1560s, 1500s, 1220s cm^{-1} .

2-Chloroacetamido-4-m-nitrophenylthiazole : It was prepared as above, crystallised from ethanol (80%), m.p. 216° (requires¹⁰ 203°). ν_{max} 3250w, 1710w 1640s, 1570s, 1530s cm^{-1} .

2-Chloroacetamido-4-p-nitrophenylthiazole : It was prepared as above. The crude product was crystallised from benzene-ethanol (3:1) (60%), m.p. 175° (Found : N, 13.76; S, 11.10. $C_{11}H_8ClN_2O_3S$

requires N, 14.11; S, 10.75%). ν_{max} 3400w, 1700w, 1660m, 1600m, 1520s cm^{-1} .

2-(N-Isobutylaminoacetamido)-4-(2',5'-dimethoxy)phenylthiazole : A mixture of 2-chloroacetamido-4-(2',5'-dimethoxy)phenylthiazole (5.0 g), isobutylamine (2.2 ml, 1.60 g), absolute ethanol (40 ml) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (2.0 g) was heated under reflux on a water bath for 12 h. The excess amine and ethanol were removed by distillation and the residue was treated with 5% sodium bicarbonate solution to remove acid impurities, filtered under suction, washed with water and dried. It was crystallised from 80% ethanol to give yellow plates (80%), m.p. 107° (Found : C, 58.30; H, 6.60; N, 12.10; S, 9.20. $C_{17}H_{22}N_4O_3S$ requires C, 58.45; H, 6.59; N, 12.03; S, 9.15%). ν_{max} 3320w, 3170w, 1740w, 1700s, 1590s, 1570s, 1500s cm^{-1} ; δ ($CDCl_3$) 0.96 [d, $J=7Hz$, 6H, $-CH(CH_3)_2$], 1.55-2.06 [m, 1H, $CH_2 - CH(CH_3)_2$], 2.51 [d, 2H, $J=6Hz$, $CH_2 - CH(CH_3)_2$], 3.50 (s, 2H, $CO.CH_2$), 3.85 and 3.93 (s, 3H each, for two OCH_3 at 5Hz separation), 5.03-6.38 (br, 2H, $NHCOCH_2NH$), 6.86-7.85 (m, 4H, Ar).

Similarly, other 2-(*N*-substituted or *N,N*-disubstituted aminoacetamido)-4-*p*-nitrophenyl, 4-*m*-nitrophenyl and 4-(2',5'-dimethoxy)phenylthiazoles were prepared by the reaction of different primary and secondary acyclic and cyclic amines with 2-chloroacetamido-4-arylthiazoles separately. These were crystallised from ethanol. Their characterisation data are given in Table I. The ir and nmr spectral data of compounds were typical of the structures assigned to them.

Hydrochloride of 2-(N-isobutylaminoacetamido)-4-(2',5'-dimethoxy)phenylthiazole : A solution of 2-(*N*-isobutylaminoacetamido)-4-(2',5'-dimethoxy)phenylthiazole (2.0 g) in anhydrous benzene was saturated with dry hydrogen chloride gas. The solid mass formed was filtered and washed with dry ether. The crude product was crystallised from ethanol to give light brown crystals, m.p. 226° (Found : C, 53.15; H, 6.16; N, 10.66; Cl, 9.32. $C_{17}H_{24}ClN_4O_3S$ requires C, 52.90; H, 6.22; N, 10.64; Cl, 9.23%).

TABLE I—CHARACTERISATION DATA OF 2-(*N*-SUBSTITUTED AND *N,N*-DISUBSTITUTED AMINOACETAMIDO)-4-ARYLTHIAZOLES (4)

Sl. No.	R_1	R_2	Yield %	m.p. °C	Colour of crystals	Molecular formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)	
							C	H
[X = <i>p</i> -NO ₂]								
1.	Et	H	80	257d	red†	$C_{14}H_{14}N_4O_3S$	51.36 (50.98)	4.68 (4.57)
2.	<i>i</i> -Pr	H	70	238	dark red	$C_{14}H_{16}N_4O_3S$	52.10 (52.50)	5.28 (5.00)
3.	<i>i</i> -Bu	H	75	271	red	$C_{16}H_{18}N_4O_3S$	53.56 (53.91)	5.52 (5.39)
4.	<i>sec</i> -Bu	H	80	258	light red	$C_{14}H_{16}N_4O_3S$	53.89 (53.91)	5.36 (5.39)
5.	<i>t</i> -Bu	H	75	240	red	$C_{16}H_{18}N_4O_3S$	53.98 (53.91)	5.45 (5.39)
6.	Et	Et	60	255	light red	$C_{16}H_{18}N_4O_3S$	54.28 (53.91)	5.26 (5.39)
7.		Piperidino	65	227	brick red	$C_{16}H_{18}N_4O_3S$	55.10 (55.49)	5.32 (5.20)

(Table 1 contd.)

[X = <i>m</i> -NO ₂]								
8.	Et	H	80	181	dark yellow	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S	50.62 (50.98)	4.48 (4.57)
9.	<i>i</i> -Pr	H	90	159	light yellow	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂ S	52.86 (52.50)	5.14 (5.00)
10.	<i>i</i> -Bu	H	90	151	yellow	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂ S	53.62 (53.91)	5.33 (5.39)
11.	<i>sec</i> -Bu	H	80	146	yellow	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂ S	53.93 (53.91)	5.36 (5.39)
12.	<i>t</i> -Bu	H	90	177	dark yellow	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂ S	54.38 (53.91)	5.12 (5.39)
[X = 2',5'-(OH ₂ O) ₂]								
13.	Et	H	**					
14.	<i>i</i> -Pr	H	60	127	yellow	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂ S	57.02 (56.69)	6.15 (6.27)
15.	<i>i</i> -Bu	H	80	107	yellow†	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₂ S	58.30 (58.45)	6.60 (6.59)
16.	<i>sec</i> -Bu	H	**					
17.	Et	Et	**					
18.		Piperidino	90	189	yellow	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂ S	60.13 (59.84)	6.32 (6.37)

* Satisfactory N and S ; ** Could not be isolated in crystalline form, directly converted into hydrochloride ; † Amorphous ; ‡ Plate.

TABLE 2—LOCAL ANAESTHETIC ACTIVITY OF 2-(*N*-SUBSTITUTED AND *N,N*-DISUBSTITUTED AMINOACETAMIDO)-4-ARYLTHIAZOLE HYDROCHLORIDES

Sl. No.	R ₁	R ₂	Yield %	m.p. °C	Colour of crystals	Onset of anaesthesia* (min.)	
						0.05 N	0.1 N
[X = <i>p</i> -NO ₂]							
1.	Et	H	60	108	yellow	10.45	11.00
2.	<i>i</i> -Pr	H	65	115	yellow	8.10	8.25
3.	<i>i</i> -Bu	H	60	117	brownish yellow	11.25	11.35
4.	<i>sec</i> -Bu	H	55	115	dirty yellow	11.30	11.40
5.	<i>t</i> -Bu	H	55	135	light yellow	11.45	12.05
6.	Et	Et	70	75	dirty yellow	11.00	11.10
7.		Piperidino	50	213	light yellow	11.10	11.25
[X = <i>m</i> -NO ₂]							
8.	Et	H	80	237	white	5.15	6.05
9.	<i>i</i> -Pr	H	75	227	white	4.55	5.50
10.	<i>i</i> -Bu	H	70	223	pale yellow	4.55	5.40
11.	<i>sec</i> -Bu	H	65	224	pale yellow	4.25	5.00
12.	<i>t</i> -Bu	H	60	225	pink	8.45	9.40
[X = 2',5'-(OH ₂ O) ₂]							
13.	Et	H	60	242	brown	8.30	8.40
14.	<i>i</i> -Pr	H	80	231	light brown	8.15	10.00
15.	<i>i</i> -Bu	H	75	226	light brown	9.50	10.20
16.	<i>sec</i> -Bu	H	65	238	brown	10.50	11.30
17.	Et	Et	65	122	brown	7.20	7.30
18.		Piperidino	75	187**	white	10.35	10.45
		Procaine hydrochloride†				10.00	10.15

* Detected by using HCl of given normality ; ** Shrinks at 165°, melts at 187° ; † 0.1% concentration, as the standard.

Following the above procedure, hydrochlorides of other 2-(*N*-substituted or *N,N*-disubstituted aminoacetamido)-4-arylthiazoles were prepared. Their yields and melting points are recorded in Table 2. Satisfactory C, H, N and Cl analyses of the hydrochlorides were obtained.

Pharmacological screening for plexus anaesthesia on frogs :

The base hydrochlorides reported in Table 2 were screened for their local anaesthetic activity on frogs at 0.1% concentration of the compounds in

0.7% saline adopting the procedure of Bulbring and Wajda⁸. Three frogs were tested for each of the compounds and the average time for onset of anaesthesia was recorded. The results (Table 2) are compared with that of procaine hydrochloride taken as the standard.

Results and Discussion

The screening results conclude that all the hydrochlorides of 2-(*N*-substituted aminoacetamido)-4-

m-nitrophenylthiazoles are relatively better in producing onset of anaesthesia in frogs in comparison to the standard substance procaine hydrochloride. Of these 2-(*N*-sec-butylaminoacetamido)-4-*m*-nitrophenylthiazole is the most potent local anaesthetic. The hydrochlorides of 2-(*N*-substituted and *N,N*-disubstituted aminoacetamido)-4-*p*-nitrophenyl and 4-(2',5'-dimethoxy)phenylthiazoles require more or less similar length of time as the standard chosen in producing onset of anaesthesia.

It is also apparent that significantly greater local anaesthetic activity of compound numbers 8-12 in comparison to that of the others is due to the presence of 4-*m*-nitrophenyl substituent. However, the *m*-nitrophenyl substituent does not confer the same degree of potency as the *p*-fluorophenyl substituent reported in our earlier communication¹.

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